

ЧАСТОТА РОЗВИТКУ МІКРОАНГІОПАТІЇ ПРИ ЦУКРОВОМУ ДІАБЕТІ (ЗА ДАНИМИ КАПІЛЯРОСКОПІЇ)

FREQUENCY OF MICROANGIOPATHY IN DIABETES MELLITUS (ACCORDING TO CAPILLAROSCOPY)

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Currently, diabetes mellitus (DM) is the most common endocrinological disease, being a major medical, social, and economic problem due to vascular complications of the disease, which lead to disability in young patients and the development of fatal complications in elderly patients.

Particular attention to the genesis of DM complications is paid to morpho-functional changes in the vascular wall. Pathological changes in blood vessels in DM are a universal morphogenetic sign of the development of complications of diabetes mellitus, which are characterized by different frequencies, prevalence, and features in each patient. The works of many researchers are devoted to the study of microcirculatory pathology in DM patients; however, there is no consensus on the morphogenesis of microangiopathy, pathogenesis, prediction, early monitoring of the process, and its prevention. Therefore, capillaroscopy is of great importance as a method of non-invasive examination of this category of patients.

The study aimed to a determination of the influence of the age of patients and duration of diabetes mellitus on the frequency of the development and severity of diabetic microangiopathy.

We observed patients (n=45) with diabetes mellitus aged 19-55 years, with different manifestations and severity of the disease. As a control group, almost healthy people (n=15) have been examined.

The study of capillary circulation was performed by microscopy of the capillaries of the skin fold of the nail bed of the 4th finger of the right and left hand and the thumb of the right and left foot using the Dino-Lite MEDL4N5 Pro capillaroscope (the Netherlands). Along with capillaroscopy, the peculiarities of the clinical course of the disease and the general condition of the patient were taken into account.

Assessing the capillaroscopic picture, attention was paid to the number, shape, and location of the vascular loops, the prominence of the subcapillary venous background, the nature of blood flow, as well as the study of individual segments of the capillary loop.

Statistical analysis of the resulting data showed that the severity of DMA was almost the same in all age groups, and insignificant differences were random ($p > 0.05$).

The probability for the development of DMA in patients with diabetes mellitus in the first 5 years of the disease accounts for 65%. Among patients with the disease for 6-10 years, DMA was detected in 94.1%. With a disease duration of more than 10 years, the small vessels of the skin were affected in all patients (100%) with various degrees of severity.

Thus, the findings of the study allow the physician to assume possible changes of capillaries in DM patients at different stages of the disease and on this basis, given the generalized nature of DMA, to estimate the state of the entire microcirculatory bed.

Conclusion: 1. DMA of the skin is observed in 82.4% of patients with diabetes mellitus. 2. The severity of DMA on the skin is directly dependent on the duration of the disease. 3. The use of the above indicators allows for predicting the possibility of the development of DMA in the skin and the degree of its severity at different stages of the disease.

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